

Analysis of the Implementation of Learning Evaluation in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education for Grade X Phase E Students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo

Harif Rahman Suyatno

Universitas Islam Negeri Imam Bonjol Padang
Correspondensi author email: harif.rahman.suyatno@uinib.ac.id

Remiswal

Universitas Islam Negeri Imam Bonjol Padang
Email: remiswal@uinib.ac.id

Khadijah

Universitas Islam Negeri Imam Bonjol Padang
Email: khadijahmpd@uinib.ac.id

Abstract

Learning evaluation is an essential component in the educational process to determine the achievement of learning objectives and the development of students' competencies. In Islamic Religious Education (IRE), evaluation covers cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects as an integral part of character building and religious skills development. This study aims to analyze the implementation of learning evaluation in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education for Grade X Phase E students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo, including the evaluation techniques and instruments used, the obstacles encountered, and the teachers' efforts to overcome them. This research employed a descriptive qualitative approach, with data collected through observation, interviews, and documentation. The informants consisted of Islamic Religious Education teachers and Grade X Phase E students. The data were analyzed through data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The findings show that the learning evaluation was systematically carried out through diagnostic, formative, and summative stages. The evaluation techniques included written tests, attitude observation, and worship practices. The obstacles included time limitations, large class sizes, and students' psychological factors. Teachers addressed these by applying varied evaluation methods, remedial teaching, and strengthening communication with parents.

Keywords: *learning evaluation, Islamic Religious Education, character education, student competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process that plays an important role in shaping the quality of human resources, both in terms of knowledge, attitudes, and skills. In the learning process, evaluation becomes one of the main components that functions to determine the level of achievement of learning objectives and the development of students' competencies. Evaluation not only serves as a tool to measure learning outcomes but also as a basis for improving and enhancing the quality of learning.

In the learning of Islamic Religious Education (IRE) and Character Education, evaluation has a broader scope because it assesses not only cognitive aspects but also affective and psychomotor aspects. These three aspects must be assessed in a balanced manner so that the learning objectives of Islamic Religious Education and Character Education can be optimally achieved. Therefore, the implementation of evaluation in IRE and Character Education learning must be carried out systematically, objectively, and continuously.

However, the implementation of learning evaluation often faces various challenges, such as time limitations, the large number of students, and difficulties in assessing affective and psychomotor aspects. Based on preliminary observations at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo, the implementation of evaluation in IRE and Character Education for Grade X Phase E students has been conducted through diagnostic, formative, and summative evaluations, although several obstacles were still found in its implementation.

Based on these issues, this study aims to analyze the implementation of learning evaluation in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education for Grade X Phase E students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo, including the evaluation techniques and instruments used, the challenges encountered, and the teachers' efforts to overcome these challenges.

METHODS

This study discusses the analysis of the implementation of learning evaluation in Islamic Religious Education for Grade X Phase E students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo. The approach used in this study is descriptive qualitative, aiming to provide an in-depth description of the implementation of Islamic Religious Education learning evaluation applied at the school. Data were collected through observation, interviews, and documentation involving Islamic Religious Education teachers and students as the main informants in this research. The data obtained were then analyzed qualitatively through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing, so that the

research findings could be presented systematically, objectively, and in accordance with the actual conditions found in the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Implementation of Learning Evaluation in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education for Grade X Phase E Students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo

Based on the results of observations, interviews, and documentation conducted with Islamic Religious Education (IRE) teachers of Grade X Phase E, the implementation of learning evaluation has been carried out systematically in accordance with the principles of educational evaluation. Evaluation is not only focused on measuring cognitive aspects but also covers affective and psychomotor domains, which are the main characteristics of IRE and Character Education learning.

The findings show that IRE teachers in Grade X Phase E implement evaluation in three main stages, namely initial evaluation (diagnostic), process evaluation (formative), and final evaluation (summative). Diagnostic evaluation is conducted to identify students' prior knowledge before the learning process begins. At this stage, teachers provide introductory questions related to the material to assess students' initial understanding.

Formative evaluation is carried out during the learning process through individual assignments, group discussions, presentations, and question-and-answer sessions. This type of evaluation aims to continuously monitor students' learning progress. Based on interviews with IRE teachers, formative evaluation is considered effective in identifying students' learning difficulties directly, allowing teachers to improve their instructional strategies.

Summative evaluation is conducted at the end of the material or semester through written tests and project assignments. Documentation results indicate that the evaluation instruments used have been adjusted to the Learning Outcomes (CP) and Learning Objectives (TP) applied in the school curriculum.

The findings reveal that the implementation of IRE learning evaluation has covered important aspects of the learning process, namely cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. Thus, evaluation functions not only to measure students' level of understanding but also to assess the development of their attitudes and religious skills.

B. Evaluation Techniques and Instruments in IRE Learning

In the learning process, evaluation techniques are methods used by teachers to obtain data regarding students' learning achievements, while evaluation instruments are the tools used to collect such data. In the perspective of educational science, evaluation techniques play a very important role because they serve as the basis for determining students' success in achieving learning objectives (Oemar, 2017).

Evaluation techniques can be divided into test and non-test techniques. Test techniques are used to measure students' cognitive abilities through written, oral, or practical forms, while non-test techniques are used to assess affective and psychomotor aspects through observation, interviews, assignments, and self-assessment. According to Suharsimi Arikunto (2018), the selection of evaluation techniques must be aligned with learning objectives to ensure that the results accurately and comprehensively reflect students' abilities.

In Islamic Religious Education, evaluation techniques are not only oriented toward knowledge aspects but also include attitudes and religious skills. This is because the characteristics of IRE emphasize a balance between conceptual understanding, value internalization, and the implementation of Islamic teachings in daily life. Therefore, the evaluation instruments used must accommodate these three domains, such as written tests for cognitive aspects, observation sheets for affective aspects, and practical assessments for psychomotor aspects (Purwanto, 2019).

Based on the research findings, the evaluation techniques used by IRE teachers in Grade X Phase E are quite varied. In the cognitive domain, teachers use written tests in the form of multiple-choice questions, essays, and oral quizzes. In the affective domain, evaluation is conducted through observation of attitudes, activeness, discipline, and students' responsibilities during the learning process. Meanwhile, in the psychomotor domain, evaluation is conducted through worship practices, such as Qur'an recitation, prayer practice, and presentations on religious topics.

This diversity of evaluation techniques indicates that teachers have attempted to implement authentic assessment in accordance with the characteristics of IRE and Character Education subjects. Authentic assessment plays an important role in providing a real picture of students' competencies, not only limited to memorization but also the implementation of Islamic values in daily life.

However, interview results show that IRE teachers still face limitations in preparing evaluation instruments, particularly in formulating affective assessment indicators that are objective and measurable. This remains a challenge because the affective domain is often subjective and requires continuous observation.

C. Challenges in the Implementation of IRE Learning Evaluation

In the learning process, evaluation is an important component that functions to determine the achievement level of learning objectives. Through evaluation, teachers can obtain information about students' learning progress and the effectiveness of teaching strategies. However, in practice, evaluation does not always run optimally due to various obstacles that may affect the quality of assessment results (Muhibbin, 2018). According to Nana Sudjana (2017), the success of learning evaluation is

influenced by several factors, such as students' readiness, teachers' competence in preparing assessment instruments, and supportive learning environments.

Based on the research findings, the implementation of IRE learning evaluation for Grade X Phase E students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo still faces several obstacles. One of the main challenges is the limited learning time, which causes the evaluation process to be less optimal, especially in assessing affective and psychomotor aspects that require deeper and continuous observation. In addition, the large number of students in one class also becomes a challenge for teachers in conducting individual assessments objectively and comprehensively.

Interviews with students indicate difficulties in understanding the forms of evaluation provided by teachers, especially tasks requiring deeper understanding and religious practice. Some students stated that they found written tests easier to understand than practical evaluations or attitude assessments because the success indicators were clearer.

Moreover, some students reported that nervousness and lack of self-confidence during worship practices or class presentations affected their evaluation results. This shows that students' psychological aspects also influence learning achievements, particularly in practice-based evaluations.

In general, students responded positively to the implementation of IRE learning evaluation. Most students stated that the evaluations helped them understand their level of comprehension of the material learned. However, some students expected more varied and interactive evaluation methods so that the assessment process would not feel monotonous and stressful.

These findings indicate that challenges in IRE learning evaluation are not only technical but are also influenced by students' readiness, understanding, and psychological conditions. Therefore, a more adaptive and communicative evaluation approach is needed to make the assessment process more effective and comprehensive.

D. Teachers' Efforts in Overcoming Challenges in IRE Learning Evaluation

In the evaluation process, teachers have a strategic role in ensuring that assessment activities run effectively and provide an objective picture of students' development. Various challenges that arise in evaluation require teachers to make improvements so that evaluation objectives can still be achieved. According to Anas Sudijono (2016), good evaluation depends not only on the instruments used but also on teachers' ability to adjust assessment techniques to students' characteristics and learning situations.

In Islamic Religious Education, teachers' efforts to overcome evaluation challenges become even more important because IRE does not only assess

knowledge but also attitudes and religious skills. Therefore, teachers are required to apply more adaptive, communicative, and continuous evaluation strategies so that assessment results can reflect students' competencies comprehensively (Nata, 2017).

Based on the research findings, IRE teachers at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo made several efforts to overcome evaluation challenges. One of the efforts was implementing varied evaluation methods to suit students' characteristics and abilities. Teachers did not rely solely on written tests but also combined assignments, discussions, observations, and religious practices as more comprehensive forms of evaluation.

In addition, teachers provided remedial programs for students who had not yet achieved learning mastery. This program was carried out as a follow-up to the evaluation to help students better understand the material they had not mastered. Based on interview results, students gave positive responses to the remedial program because it helped them improve their learning outcomes.

Another effort was increasing communication with homeroom teachers and parents to monitor students' learning progress and attitudes more comprehensively. This collaboration was considered important, especially in supporting character building and discipline, which are part of IRE learning objectives. Teachers also tried to create a more comfortable and less stressful evaluation atmosphere, especially in practical assessments.

The findings show that teachers' efforts in overcoming evaluation challenges are not only focused on technical aspects but also on pedagogical and psychological approaches toward students. Thus, IRE learning evaluation can be carried out more effectively and can better support the development of students' competencies..

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, the implementation of learning evaluation in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education for Grade X Phase E students at SMAN 1 Luhak Nan Duo has been carried out systematically through diagnostic, formative, and summative evaluations. The evaluation covers cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects by employing various assessment techniques and instruments. However, the implementation of evaluation still faces several challenges, such as limited time, a large number of students, and difficulties in assessing affective and psychomotor aspects. To overcome these challenges, teachers have made various efforts, such as applying varied evaluation methods, providing remedial programs, and improving communication with parents and homeroom teachers. Overall, the implementation of learning evaluation in Islamic Religious Education and Character Education has been

carried out quite well and needs to be continuously developed to become more effective and optimal.

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